

Willis metamaterial on a structured beam

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Abstract

Bianisotropy is common in electromagnetism whenever a cross-coupling between electric and magnetic responses exists. However, the analogous concept for elastic waves in solids, termed as Willis coupling, is more challenging to observe. It requires coupling between stress and velocity or momentum and strain fields, which is difficult to induce in non-negligible levels, even when using metamaterial structures. Here, we report the experimental realization of a Willis metamaterial for flexural waves. Based on a cantilever bending resonance, we demonstrate asymmetric reflection amplitudes and phases due to Willis coupling. We also show that, by introducing loss in the metamaterial, the asymmetric amplitudes can be controlled and can be used to approach an exceptional point of the non-Hermitian system, at which unidirectional zero reflection occurs. The present work extends conventional propagation theory in plates and beams to include Willis coupling, and provides new avenues to tailor flexural waves using artificial structures.

I. INTRODUCTION

Metamaterials, constructed with artificially designed microstructures, have been employed and developed in electromagnetism [1,2], acoustics [3-7], thermodynamics [8,9] and mechanics [10-12] to give unique properties beyond those provided by natural and composite materials. Such a concept has recently been extended to elastic waves in solids [13-17]. Compared to acoustic waves, the additional degrees of freedom in polarizations states require more sophisticated dispersion engineering [18-20] and also lead to non-trivial mode-matching at interfaces. Metamaterials are found particularly useful as a tool to explore the physics behind this complexity. For example, for in-plane waves, a trans-modal Fabry-Pérot condition is found necessary for maximum mode conversion between longitudinal and shear modes [21]. For flexural waves [22,23], evanescent modes can be used to modify surface impedance for obtaining higher transmission than structures in acoustics [24].

Peculiarly, classical elastic wave equations, i.e. the Hooke's law together with the Newton's second law, are not form-invariant under a coordinate transformation [25,26], suggesting that we are currently exploring an unnecessarily limited palette of material properties. For example, an introduction of rotation modulus in Hooke's law [27] is found necessary to describe biological composites such as wet bones [28]. This is called a Cosserat solid or a micropolar medium and has been recently constructed using metamaterial approach [29]. Another attempt is the proposal to realize Willis media [30]. These media introduce new constitutive terms not only in Hooke's law but also in Newton's second law [31-35]. These terms, which introduce coupling between stress and velocity and between momentum and strain, are typically small perturbations and difficult to realize. Currently, a similar modification to both equations was experimentally introduced in airborne acoustics [36-38], and a strategy to induce strong Willis coupling in suitably designed acoustic metamaterials was

theoretically introduced [39]. The acoustic wave equations, when Willis coupling is considered, can be written in analogy to the electromagnetic scenario, and the additional constitutive terms correspond to bianisotropy in electromagnetism [40-43]. These developments indicate that Willis media for elastic waves in solid, may become practical through the notion of metamaterials, although the exact microstructural design has yet to be determined.

In this work, we consider the situation when a Willis medium is used to construct a plate or a beam for flexural wave propagation. Such a reduced version from three to two dimensions facilitates analysis and an intuitive understanding of Willis coupling. Plates and beams are actually common in a wide range of length scales from building structures to micromechanical systems. Their theories can be traced back to the 1950s to 1980s in a series of works from Kirchhoff-Love plate theory to extensions with rotary and shear deformations, and from isotropic to anisotropic plates and beams [44,45]. However, further extension to include Willis coupling to plate theory is deemed necessary to open new directions in this field of research, especially on the design of seismic metamaterials for earthquake protection [14,22,46]. The special responses offered by artificially tunable Willis coupling, including asymmetric reflection amplitudes and exceptional points, open an unexplored territory for ultrasonic nondestructive evaluation, seismology and micro-sensor technology [14,46-48].

II. WILLIS PLATE AND BEAM THEORY

We start from a Willis medium, with constitutive relation in its most general form [33]:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{ij} &= C_{ijkl}\varepsilon_{kl} - \omega^2 S_{ijk}u_k, \\ p_j &= -i\omega S_{klj}\varepsilon_{kl} - i\omega\rho_{ij}u_i,\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where C and ρ are the stiffness and density tensors, ω is the radial frequency and i, j, k are indices iterating the spatial coordinates. The additional S term in Hooke's law, Willis coupling coefficient,

couples stress σ to displacement u and the same term (due to reciprocity) in Newton's second law couples momentum p to strain ε . Suppose that we now construct a plate ($z = -h/2$ to $h/2$) from this medium. By integrating Eq. (1) along z (zereth moment), we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q_x &= 2\mu h \varepsilon_{xz} - \omega^2 h \tau u_z, \\ P_z &= -2i\omega h \tau \varepsilon_{xz} - i\omega \rho_{zz} h u_z. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

We assume flexural wave propagation along the x -direction ($\partial_y \rightarrow 0$, $u_y = 0$). Eq. (2) relates the shear force $Q_x = \int \sigma_{xz} dz$ and the total momentum $P_z = \int p_z dz$ to u_z and ε_{xz} . μ and ρ_{zz} are recognized as the effective shear modulus and density along z for the plate. The additional constant τ (it is actually S_{xzz} in the bulk) is a Willis coupling term. For plate theory, we actually need to integrate up to the first moment ($\int z dz$) of Eq. (1) and the equation of motion, yielding

$$\partial_x^2 (D \partial_z \varepsilon_{xx}) + \frac{h^3 \omega^2}{12} \partial_x (\varrho_{xx} \partial_z u_x) = \partial_x Q_x = -i\omega P_z \quad (3)$$

which has the same form in Mindlin plate theory [44], but now with Willis coupling terms in Q_x and P_z to describe propagation of u_x and u_z . D is the bending stiffness defined for either the plate [49]. The second term involving ϱ_{xx} , effective density along x , refers to rotary motion, which can be neglected when the plate is sufficiently thin. Furthermore, if we use the Willis material to construct a narrow beam (confining the width of the plate in the y -direction), Eq. (2) stays exactly the same with the same values of coefficients while Eq. (3) stay the same form but with the values of D and ϱ_{xx} renormalized from a plate to a beam version (see Appendix A for more details). Therefore, Eqs. (2) and (3) describe wave propagation along x -direction for a Willis plate or beam although we have not yet designed the mechanism to generate the required Willis coupling. We also note that there can be possibly a higher-order Willis coupling term in the first moment (which will appear inside the two brackets in Eq. (3)), but its effect is negligible for subwavelength inclusions, see the κ term for details

in Appendix A).

III. METAMATERIAL DESIGN WITH WILLIS COUPLING

As the Willis coupling term τ comes from S_{xzz} of the bulk, a necessary condition to have non-zero τ is broken mirror symmetry in the x -direction. Figure 1(a) shows the unit cell of the metamaterial plate designed by perforating slots in a background acrylic plate. The inner disk is connected to the matrix by two thin ribs, either along the y -direction (as a reference case without Willis coupling in the next section), or both connected to the back interface (as in the case with Willis coupling). The various dimensions of the structure are listed in the caption. In the latter case, there is a cantilever bending resonance for the central disk at around 14.5 kHz [50], designed to implement a strong Willis coupling: when there is a constant force F_z applied along the z -direction on both the front and back interfaces, a typical simulated displacement profile u_z around the resonating frequency is shown as the color map. The back interface, being dragged by the disk, has a smaller magnitude of displacement than the front interface. This asymmetry gives rise to non-zero Willis coupling between P_z (equivalent to F_z) and ε_{xz} in Eq. (2).

FIG. 1. Symmetry breaking in reflection and Willis metamaterial. (a) Symmetric metamaterial is changed into the Willis one by breaking mirror symmetry. For this Willis material, $a_0 = 5.0 \text{ mm}$, $h_0 = 2.0 \text{ mm}$, $r_1 = 0.45a_0$, $r_2 = 0.25a_0$, and $d = 0.5 \text{ mm}$ with orientation angles of two thin ribs 150 and 210 degrees, respectively. The displacement field u_z is plotted by loading force F_z (shown as black arrows). The field of u_z on the two end surfaces are also presented by blue arrows. The Willis material is assembled as a metamaterial layer in a thin beam. Forward/backward plane wave is incident into the left/right side of the beam. (b) Amplitudes $|r|$ and phases $\text{Arg}(r)$ of reflected waves from both sides for lossless material (density $\rho_0 = 1190 \text{ kg/m}^3$, Young's modulus $E_0 = 2.95 \text{ GPa}$ and Poisson ratio $\nu_0 = 0.29$). (c) Amplitudes $|r|$ and phases $\text{Arg}(r)$ of reflected waves for lossy material (the

Young's modulus turns into $E_0 = 2.95(1 - 0.05i)GPa$. (d) Effective parameters at different frequencies. (e) Theoretical values of reflection amplitudes $|r|$ and phases $\text{Arg}(r)$ for lossy material. In (b), (c) and (e), the solid/dashed lines correspond to the case of forward/backward incident waves.

This asymmetry of displacement field is connected to asymmetric reflection. Suppose that 5 unit cells are cascaded and embedded in the background plate. The forward and backward reflection amplitudes, r_f and r_b , are obtained by full-wave simulations from 7 to 12 kHz (corresponding to wavelengths from 28.1 to 21.2 mm) and are plotted in Fig. 1(b). As the metamaterial is reciprocal, we have equal transmission t in both directions and hence the same magnitude of reflection amplitude if the material is lossless: $|r_f|^2 = 1 - |t|^2 = |r_b|^2$. The asymmetry of reflection only shows up in the phase and becomes most prominent at 7.7 and 11.0 kHz, in which Fabry-Pérot (FP) resonances [51] for elastic waves occur at the reflection amplitude dips. If we add an material loss (by adding 5% of the real part of Young's modulus to the imaginary part), the magnitude of the reflection amplitudes become asymmetric as well, as shown in Fig. 1(c).

The asymmetry in reflection can be understood in terms of the Willis coupling parameter. First, we define an effective medium model of our structure from the eigenmode profiles (see Appendix B for details). The normalized bending stiffness $\tilde{D} = D/D_0$, normalized density $\tilde{\rho} = \rho/\rho_0$, and normalized Willis coupling parameter $\tilde{\tau} = \frac{\tau}{\mu} \frac{\omega^2}{k_0}$ are plotted in Fig. 1(d). These are the minimal set of dimensionless parameters for our case to describe the metamaterial with an effective medium model. D_0 , ρ_0 and k_0 are the corresponding bending stiffness, density and wave number for the background beam. Then, the transfer matrix can be formulated numerically from the effective medium with thickness of 5 unit cells and the reflection amplitudes (for the lossy case) are plotted in Fig. 1(e),

showing similar behavior to full-wave simulation. In the long wavelength limit, the transfer matrix can be simplified analytically, giving rise to a difference of reflection amplitudes $r_f - r_b \approx -\tilde{\tau}k_0le^{-ik_0l}$, where l is the total thickness of the metamaterial (see Appendix C for details). This provides a qualitative understanding of the contribution of the Willis coupling to asymmetric reflection. When we turn off $\tilde{\tau}$ by setting it to zero, the reflection amplitudes become the same for both directions as expected (results not shown). Besides that, we obtain similar wave propagation behaviors and effective parameters for Willis materials in a structured plate [50], indicating that the present design works not only in beams but also in plate-like structures.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION OF WILLIS PROPERTIES

A series of experimental studies have been carried out to demonstrate Willis coupling and the resultant asymmetric reflection. Figure 2(a) shows the photographs of two experimental samples, with geometric dimensions listed in the caption. The top one shows our designed Willis material while the bottom one shows a symmetric metamaterial. Several unit cells for either structure are 3D printed (using a Stratasys Objet30 Pro 3D printer, based on photo-polymerization) as a structured beam with length, width and thickness 280.0, 5.0 and 2.0mm, respectively. OBJET VEROBLUE RGD840 (acrylic) is chosen as the printing material, with measured materials parameters Young's modulus $E_0 = 2.95(1 - 0.04i)$ GPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu_0 = 0.29$ and density $\rho_0 = 1190$ kg/m³. A 5-cycle tone burst with the central frequency of 10 kHz is defined in a signal generator channel of a scanning laser vibrometer (Polytec PSV-400). After the amplification of a power amplifier (KH 7602M), the pulse signal transfers to a piezoelectric transducer to generate flexural plane waves from the left (forward) or the right (backward) directions. Blue-tack is attached on both ends of each beam as absorbers to diminish reflected waves. The out-of-plane displacement field (160 mm length in the central area, with

a spatial resolution of 2.0 mm) are tested by the laser vibrometer. After the fast Fourier transform (FFT), the wave field at each frequency is obtained and used to further extract the transmission and reflection spectrum (see Appendix D for details).

Figure 2(b) shows the reflection amplitudes given by the Willis material, shown by the blue and red symbols for 5 and 3 unit cells respectively. The reflection amplitude ($|r_b|$) in the backward direction is smaller than the one ($|r_f|$) in the forward direction. Such an asymmetry is most prominent near the FP resonances: the reflection dips at 7.6 kHz and 11.0 kHz for the 5-unit cells sample, where the difference of reflection amplitude $\Delta|r| = |r_f| - |r_b|$ reaches to local maximums 0.10 and 0.18, and at 9.0 kHz for the 3-unit cells sample, where the difference reaches to 0.08. This indicates that our system actually exhibits certain amount of material loss (as assumed in last section). The multiple reflections near the FP condition within the unit cells forces the waves to interact more strongly with the bending cantilever resonance, and hence the asymmetry in amplitude becomes larger. On the contrary, the grey symbols in the same figure show the forward and backward reflection amplitude for a similar structure (but symmetric), in which no asymmetric reflection occurs. The observed asymmetry in reflection also agrees well with full-wave simulation results, shown in Fig. 2(c). For example, the Willis material with 3 unit cells, exhibits the same FP dip at 8.6 kHz with quantitative agreement $\Delta|r| = 0.09$ to the experiment.

FIG. 2. Experimental testing of asymmetric reflection and extraction of Willis coupling. (a) Photograph of Willis and symmetric metamaterials. (b) and (c) The experimentally tested and simulated reflected amplitude of different cases, respectively. For the symmetric material, $r_1 = 0.4a_0$, $d = 0.4\text{mm}$ with orientation angles of two thin ribs along the y -direction are set. Other geometric and material parameters are same to the Willis case. (d)-(f) The theoretical (solid lines) and experimental (symbols) values of the even scattering coefficient s_{ee} , the odd scattering coefficient s_{oo} and the cross-coupling scattering coefficient s_c of the Willis metamaterial.

As we have measured the complex transmission and reflection coefficients for excitation from both sides, we can reveal Willis coupling directly by plotting the even and odd scattering coefficients. Similar to the case of electromagnetic metamaterials [52,53], materials without bianisotropy only convert even (odd) inputs to even (odd) scattered waves (termed as s_{ee} and s_{oo}). The Willis coupling here contributes a cross-coupling between even input and odd output or equivalently between odd

input and even output (termed as s_c , it represents $s_{eo} = -s_{oe}$ with the same amplitude but minus sign from reciprocity [32,33]). Figs. 2(d)-(f) show the even scattering coefficient s_{ee} , the odd scattering coefficient s_{oo} and the cross-coupling scattering coefficient s_c . First, the scattering matrix (parameters t , r_f and r_b) can be either measured from experiment for a sample with only one unit cell or obtained from theory: the unit cell scattering matrix resultant from the effective medium in Fig. 1(d). Then, the even and odd scattering coefficients can be obtained by linearly combining the matrix elements (see Appendix E for details). In our case, a non-zero cross-coupling scattering coefficient s_c (approximated by $-0.1 + (0.24 - 0.04f)i$ with f being the frequency in kHz), directly reveals the effective “bianisotropy” given by Willis materials. Moreover, due to symmetry breaking, the bending cantilever resonance can now be excited by both even and odd inputs, giving rise to s_{oo} and s_{ee} . In contrary, s_c becomes zero if a mirror symmetric structure is used for testing.

FIG. 3. Tunable asymmetry by loading lossy porous rubber. (a) Schematic of adding loss by attaching soft porous rubber patches to the metamaterial layer. (b) Measured amplitudes of the reflected waves $|r|$ with and without porous rubber patches. (c) Eigenvalues of the S matrix at different frequencies for a 5-unit-Willis metamaterial layer, with soft porous rubber patches attached on surfaces. Green arrows represent the trajectories of both eigenvalues along with the increase of the frequency. (d) Eigenvalues of the S matrix at different frequencies for a 1-unit-Willis metamaterial layer, no soft porous rubber pasted. The case of ideal lossless layer is a perfect unit circle. (e) Amplitude difference of reflected waves $\Delta|r| = |r_f| - |r_b|$. (f) Phase difference of reflected waves $\Delta\phi = \text{Arg}(r_f/r_b)$ for both cases.

V. TUNABLE ASYMMETRY BY VARYING THE LOSS COEFFICIENT

Next, we show that the degree of asymmetry and also the frequencies (the FP dips) where the asymmetry occurs can be easily tuned by loading additional materials with loss to the Willis metamaterial. Here, soft porous silicon rubber synthesized by thermal polymerization [54] is pasted onto the upper and lower surfaces of the metamaterial layer (with 5 unit cells), as schematically shown in Fig. 3(a). Figure 3(b) shows the experimental reflection amplitudes for metamaterials with soft porous rubbers (with thickness of 2mm and porosity of 12%). Apart from tuning the loss, the pasted porous rubber largely changes the band structure and eigenmodes of the metamaterial, which leads to a different set of effective material parameters. As a result, a FP dip is observed at 10.24 kHz. Furthermore, when an appropriate amount of loss is added to the metamaterial, the reflection dip actually approaches to zero (for one direction), yielding the so-called unidirectional zero reflection (UZR) [50]. For the case with two porous rubber sheets loaded, the reflection dip in the forward direction attains a value of 0.004, very close to zero, while the reflection amplitude in the other direction is around 0.128. The quality of the UZR can also be visualized by examining the eigenvalues of the scattering matrix S in the complex plane. For a non-Hermitian system, like the one at hand, the eigenvalue degeneracy of the scattering matrix is called exceptional point of the system and a UZR occurs exactly at that point [53]. As shown in Fig. 3(c), trajectories against frequency for both eigenvalues of S first move towards each other, approaching the exceptional point at 10.24 kHz and then split again with increasing frequency. If we can tune the loss in a finer degree than the current experiment, it is possible to further improve the quality by bringing the two trajectories even closer to each other [50]. On the contrary, we also plot the eigenvalues of S for the case with only one unit cell (without the porous rubber sheet loading) in Fig. 3(d). In this case, loss is reduced, and it does not

support FP resonances to create large asymmetry in reflection amplitudes. In such a case, the eigenvalues are non-degenerate and are located near to the unit circle corresponding to the lossless case.

In fact, the loading of porous rubber sheets can be an effective way to tune not only the UZR frequency position but also the degree of reflection asymmetry, on both $\Delta|r| = |r_f| - |r_b|$ and the phase difference $\Delta\phi = \arg(r_f/r_b)$. Figure 3(e) shows that measured $\Delta|r|$, which changes from positive to negative by the additional loading of porous rubber sheets. Such a change occurs over wide frequency bandwidth as well. Figure 3(f) shows the phase difference between the two directions. $\Delta\phi$ becomes large and can cover the whole 2π range. This is due to the current employment of the FP resonance in creating the asymmetry combined with the UZR (the most extreme asymmetry from an exceptional point) for the two-sheets case, in contrary to the demonstrated case airborne-acoustic bianisotropy [37], and further illustrates a non-trivial feature of our lossy Willis materials.

VI. DISCUSSION

By extending conventional plate and beam theory with the introduction of Willis materials, we have designed and experimentally realized effective bianisotropy in a Willis metamaterial for elastic waves using a cantilever-type resonating structure. The metamaterial induces cross-coupling between shear force and vertical displacement of the plate, or equivalently between vertical momentum and shear strain. The present design works for flexural waves on both plate-like and beam-like structures. The effective medium parameters, including the Willis coupling, are confirmed through experimental measurements of the asymmetric reflection amplitudes in the forward and backward propagation directions. Unlike previous studies on acoustic bianisotropic materials, not only asymmetric phases but also asymmetric amplitudes of reflection are observed due to the presence of loss, whose effect is

further magnified through a combination of the cantilever bending resonance and a FP resonance. Interestingly, by incorporating an appropriate amount of loss, we have demonstrated the most asymmetric case in which the reflection amplitude goes to zero in one direction. Unidirectional zero reflection is achieved when approaching the exceptional point of the scattering matrix if the metamaterial is interpreted as a non-Hermitian system. Together with the demonstrated tunability of the responses (asymmetric reflection amplitudes, phases and frequency dips), the proposed metamaterials operating at the exceptional point can be applied to realize high-Q sensors [55,56], tunable metasurfaces and asymmetric wavefront control [57]. Elastic bianisotropy for scalar flexural waves can be generalized to Lamb waves for intermodal conversion control, to Rayleigh waves in seismology for earthquake protection of civil buildings, or to obtain high transmission efficiency [14, 46, 58-61]. The demonstration of Willis metamaterial can also be used as a typical prototype to design transformation elastic devices, as for its original motivation, to construct an elastic wave cloak based on form-invariant transformations of elastic wave equations [25, 46,62].

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APPENDIX A: FIRST-ORDER WILLIS PLATE AND BEAM THEORY

When a Willis medium, with \mathcal{M}_y and \mathcal{M}_z mirror symmetry, is in the form of a thin plate of thickness

h , we take $\sigma_{zz} \cong 0$. Eq. (1) can then be rewritten in the form as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{yz} \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} C_{xzxx} & 0 \\ 0 & C_{yzyz} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2\varepsilon_{xz} \\ 2\varepsilon_{yz} \end{pmatrix} - \omega^2 \begin{pmatrix} S_{xzz} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} u_z \\ p_z &= -i\omega(S_{xzz}2\varepsilon_{xz} + \rho_{zz}u_z) \\ \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{pmatrix} &= [C^{(p)}] \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ 2\varepsilon_{xy} \end{pmatrix} - \omega^2[S^{(p)}] \begin{pmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} p_x \\ p_y \end{pmatrix} &= -i\omega \left([S^{(p)}]^T \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ 2\varepsilon_{xy} \end{pmatrix} + [\rho_T^{(p)}] \begin{pmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \end{pmatrix} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (A1)$$

where $[C^{(p)}]$, $[S^{(p)}]$ and $[\rho_T^{(p)}]$ have matrices elements renormalized from the bulk constitutive parameters to the plate ones (indicated by superscript (p)). For a Mindlin plate, we only need to consider up to the first two moments of above equations. Integrating the first two equations in Eq. (A1)

by $\int dz$ and integrating the last two equations by $\int zdz$ gives Eq. (2) and

$$\begin{aligned} M_{xx} &= D\partial_z\varepsilon_{xx} - \omega^2 \frac{h^3}{12} \kappa\partial_z u_x \\ N_x &= -\frac{i\omega h^3}{12} \kappa\partial_z\varepsilon_{xx} - \frac{i\omega h^3}{12} \varrho_{xx}\partial_z u_x \end{aligned} \quad (A2)$$

where $M_{xx} = \int z\sigma_{xx}dz$, $N_x = \int zp_x dz$, $\kappa = S_{xxx}^{(p)}$, $\varrho_{xx} = \rho_{xx}^{(p)}$, and $D = h^3 C_{xxxx}^{(p)}/12$ is called the bending stiffness. The coefficients $C_{xxxx}^{(p)}$, $S_{xxx}^{(p)}$ and $\rho_{xx}^{(p)}$ for the plate can be expressed in terms of the bulk parameters through

$$\begin{aligned} C_{xxxx}^{(p)} &= C_{xxxx} - (C_{xxzz})^2/C_{zzzz} \\ S_{xxx}^{(p)} &= S_{xxx} - C_{xxzz}S_{zzx}/C_{zzzz} \\ \rho_{xx}^{(p)} &= \rho_{xx} + \omega^2(S_{zzx})^2/C_{zzzz} \end{aligned}$$

We have also used $\partial_y \rightarrow 0$ and $u_y = 0$ in writing Eq. (2) and Eq. (A2) as the constitutive relationship for a flexural wave propagating along the x -direction on the plate. We note that in deriving Eq. (A2), we have taken the approximation that the field quantities being odd functions in z are linear in z . On

the other hand, the even(-in-z) field quantities are assumed to be constant in z. It can be further improved by using a quadratic function in z so that an additional shear correction multiplication factor appears in front of μ for example. Here, we have not employed such a higher-order correction for brevity as it will not affect the form.

If the Willis medium is in the form of a narrow beam of width b in the y-direction, Eq. (A1) is further modified by taking $\sigma_{yy} \cong 0$, as

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{xz} &= C_{xzzxz} 2\varepsilon_{xz} - \omega^2 S_{xzz} u_z, \\
p_z &= -i\omega(S_{xzz} 2\varepsilon_{xz} + \rho_{zz} u_z), \\
\sigma_{xx} &= C_{xxxx}^{(b)} \varepsilon_{xx} - \omega^2 S_{xxx}^{(b)} u_x, \\
p_x &= -i\omega\left(S_{xxx}^{(b)} \varepsilon_{xx} + \rho_{xx}^{(b)} u_x\right),
\end{aligned} \tag{A3}$$

for the flexural wave propagating on the narrow beam along the x-direction. The coefficients $C_{xxxx}^{(p)}$, $S_{xxx}^{(p)}$ and $\rho_{xx}^{(p)}$ are further renormalized from the plate to the beam version through

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{xxxx}^{(b)} &= C_{xxxx}^{(p)} - \left(C_{xxyy}^{(p)}\right)^2 / C_{yyyy}^{(p)} \\
S_{xxx}^{(b)} &= S_{xxx}^{(p)} - C_{xxyy}^{(p)} S_{yyx}^{(p)} / C_{yyyy}^{(p)} \\
\rho_{xx}^{(b)} &= \rho_{xx}^{(p)} + \omega^2 \left(S_{yyx}^{(p)}\right)^2 / C_{yyyy}^{(p)}
\end{aligned}$$

The first two moments of Eq. (A3) then give the constitutive relationship for the beam: exactly the same Eq. (2) and another equation of the same form as Eq. (A2) except $\kappa = S_{xxx}^{(b)}$, $q_{xx} = \rho_{xx}^{(b)}$, $D = h^3 C_{xxxx}^{(b)} / 12$ being changed from the plate to the beam version. For isotropic material with Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν as a trivial example, the above formulation gives bending stiffness as $h^3 E / 12 / (1 - \nu^2)$ for a plate and $h^3 E / 12$ for a beam. Again, we have neglected additional shear correction factor by just approximating the field quantities being even in y to be constant for simplicity. The form of Eq. (A2) stays the same for either a plate or a beam although the values of the coefficients

change. We will use Eq. (A2) interchangeably for both a Willis plate and a Willis beam.

On the other hand, the wave equations for flexural waves along the x -direction on a plate (in the level of Mindlin plate theory) or along a narrow beam (in the level of Timoshenko beam theory) [44] share a common form as

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_x M_{xx} &= Q_x - i\omega N_x, \\ \partial_x Q_x &= -i\omega P_z,\end{aligned}\tag{A4}$$

disregarding whether the constitutive relationship has or has no Willis terms. It can be obtained by either taking moments (in z) from the bulk wave equations or by Hamilton's principle on the plate Lagrangian $\int \mathcal{L} dz$ for a plate or $\int \mathcal{L} dy dz$ for a beam with Lagrangian density $\mathcal{L} = (p_i \partial_t u_i - \varepsilon_{ij} \sigma_{ij})/2$. It is noted that Eqs. (A2) and (A4) will lead to Eq. (3) if we omit the Willis coupling term κ . Together with the geometric relation $\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial_j u_i + \partial_i u_j)$, we can express the governing equations (Eq. (2), Eq. (A2) and Eq. (A4)) in a combined form as

$$-i\Pi\partial_x \begin{pmatrix} u_z \\ \partial_z u_x \\ M_{xx} \\ Q_x \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h\omega^2 \left(\rho_{zz} + \frac{\tau^2 \omega^2}{\mu} \right) & 0 & 0 & \frac{\tau \omega^2}{\mu} \\ 0 & \frac{h^3 \omega^2}{12} \left(Q_{xx} + \frac{h^3 \kappa^2 \omega^2}{12D} \right) & \frac{h^3 \kappa \omega^2}{12D} & -1 \\ 0 & \frac{h^3 \kappa \omega^2}{12D} & \frac{1}{D} & 0 \\ \frac{\tau \omega^2}{\mu} & -1 & 0 & \frac{1}{h\mu} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u_z \\ \partial_z u_x \\ M_{xx} \\ Q_x \end{pmatrix}\tag{A5}$$

with

$$\Pi = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

APPENDIX B: EFFECTIVE MATERIAL PARAMETERS RETRIEVAL METHOD

From Eq. (A5), we can obtain the dispersion relationship as

$$Dk^2 + \frac{h\omega^2(\mu\rho_z + \tau^2\omega^2)}{\rho_z\omega^2 - k^2\mu} = \frac{h^3\omega^2\rho_{xx}}{12} \quad (\text{B1})$$

where k is the wave number. It is noted that κ does not go into the dispersion relationship. Based on Eq. (B1), the field of $\partial_z u_x$ can be expressed as

$$\partial_z u_x = \alpha_f e^{ikx} + \beta_f e^{-Kx} + \alpha_b e^{-ikx} + \beta_b e^{Kx} \quad (\text{B2})$$

where α_f/α_b and β_f/β_b are the amplitudes of the propagating and evanescent waves in the forward/backward direction, respectively and

$$k^2 = \frac{\omega\sqrt{\Gamma} + \Delta}{24D\mu}, \quad K^2 = \frac{\omega\sqrt{\Gamma} - \Delta}{24D\mu} \quad (\text{B3})$$

with $\Gamma = 576Dh\mu^2(\rho_{zz} + \omega^2\tau^2/\mu) + \omega^2(h^3\mu\rho_{xx} - 12D\rho_{zz})^2$ and $\Delta = (h^3\mu\rho_{xx} + 12D\rho_{zz})\omega^2$. By neglecting the shear and rotary effects by supposing $\mu \rightarrow \infty$ and $\rho_{xx} \rightarrow 0$ based on the thin beam theory [44], we have $k = K = \sqrt[4]{\rho'_{zz}h\omega^2/D}$ with $\rho'_{zz} = \rho_{zz} + \omega^2\tau^2/\mu$. On the interface between two different media, Eq. (A5) suggests the continuity of $u_z k_0$, $\partial_z u_x$, $M_{xx}/(D_0 k_0)$ and $Q_x/(D_0 k_0^2)$, where the subscript “0” means the values in the background medium. Thus the continuity matrix M may be written as

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{in + \tilde{\tau}}{n^2} & \frac{n - \tilde{\tau}}{n^2} & \frac{-in + \tilde{\tau}}{n^2} & \frac{-n + \tilde{\tau}}{n^2} \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ in\tilde{D} - \tilde{\kappa}\tilde{D} & -n\tilde{D} - \tilde{\kappa}\tilde{D} & -in\tilde{D} - \tilde{\kappa}\tilde{D} & n\tilde{D} - \tilde{\kappa}\tilde{D} \\ -n^2\tilde{D} & n^2\tilde{D} & -n^2\tilde{D} & n^2\tilde{D} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B4})$$

with the continuous value of $M \cdot \{\alpha_f, \beta_f, \alpha_b, \beta_b\}$ on the interface, where $\tilde{D} = D/D_0$ is dimensionless bending stiffness, $\tilde{\tau} = \frac{\tau}{\mu} \frac{\omega^2}{k_0}$ and $\tilde{\kappa} = \frac{\kappa h^3}{12D} \frac{\omega^2}{k_0}$ are dimensionless Willis coupling terms, and $\tilde{\rho} = \rho'_{zz}/\rho_0 = n^4\tilde{D}$ is the dimensionless density with $n = k/k_0$.

Eq. (B4) gives us a way to calculate the effective medium parameters of the metamaterial.

Specifically, the eigenmodes at different values of k are obtained from full-wave simulations and the

effective fields can be obtained by

$$\begin{aligned}
u_z &= \frac{1}{A} \int u_z(y, z) dA, \\
\partial_z u_x &= \frac{1}{A} \int \partial_z u_x(y, z) dA, \\
M_{xx} &= \frac{h}{A} \int z \sigma_{xx}(y, z) dA, \\
Q_x &= \frac{h}{A} \int \sigma_{xz}(y, z) dA
\end{aligned} \tag{B5}$$

where the integrations are performed on the cross-section of the unit cell, with area A and perpendicular to the wave propagation direction in x . Then the effective material parameters can be obtained based on Eq. (B4) by

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{D} &= \frac{\delta}{D_0 k^2}, \\
\tilde{\rho} &= \frac{k^2 \delta}{\rho_0 h \omega^2}, \\
\tilde{\kappa} &= -\frac{k^2}{k_0 \delta} \text{Re}(M_{xx} / \partial_z u_x), \\
\tilde{\tau} &= -\frac{k^2 \delta}{k_0} \frac{\text{Re}(u_z / \partial_z u_x)}{\text{Re}(Q_x / \partial_z u_x)}
\end{aligned} \tag{B6}$$

with $\delta = \sqrt{\frac{\text{Im}(M_{xx} / \partial_z u_x) \text{Re}(-Q_x / \partial_z u_x)}{\text{Im}(u_z / \partial_z u_x)}}$. Figure 4 shows the simulated results of the effective parameters.

In the long-wavelength limit, $\tilde{\rho} \rightarrow 0.6$ matches the analytic value given by the filling fraction. Besides that, both dimensionless Willis coupling terms $\tilde{\kappa}$ and $\tilde{\tau}$ are nearly zero at low frequencies. As expected, the amplitude of zeroth order Willis coupling $\tilde{\tau}$ is much larger than the first order Willis coupling $\tilde{\kappa}$ and shows significant values in the range of 7 to 12 kHz.

FIG. 4. Dimensionless effective parameters of the Willis metamaterial with respect to the frequency.

APPENDIX C: ASYMMETRIC REFLECTION OF THE WILLIS METAMATERIAL

Comparing the first and third columns of M in Eq. (B4), we can find different eigenmodes in the positive and negative directions, leading to asymmetric wave propagation behaviors. For flexural waves incident from the background medium to a metamaterial layer with length l , the total transfer matrix T can be written as

$$T = M_0^{-1} \cdot M \cdot N \cdot M^{-1} \cdot M_0 \quad (\text{C1})$$

where M_0 is the continuity matrix of the background medium, and

$$N = \begin{bmatrix} e^{ikl} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-kl} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{-ikl} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & e^{kl} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C2})$$

with $\{\alpha_{f,L}, \beta_{f,L}, \alpha_{b,L}, \beta_{b,L}\}^T = T \cdot \{\alpha_{f,R}, \beta_{f,R}, \alpha_{b,R}, \beta_{b,R}\}^T$. Subscripts “L” and “R” indicate the left and right sides of the system. Then the scattering matrix \hat{S} in terms of $\partial_z u$ with $\{\alpha_{f,R}, \beta_{f,R}, \alpha_{b,L}, \beta_{b,L}\}^T = \hat{S} \cdot \{\alpha_{f,L}, \beta_{f,L}, \alpha_{b,R}, \beta_{b,R}\}^T$ can be easily obtained. If only the propagating modes are considered, the 4×4 scattering matrix \hat{S} turns into a 2×2 one. Considering that $\partial_z u_x \cong -\partial_x u_z$ in a thin beam, we have $u_z = \frac{i}{k} \alpha_f e^{ikx} + \frac{1}{K} \beta_f e^{-Kx} - \frac{i}{k} \alpha_b e^{-ikx} - \frac{1}{K} \beta_b e^{Kx}$. Thus the 2×2 scattering matrix with respect to the displacement field u_z should be

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{S}_{11} & -\hat{S}_{13} \\ -\hat{S}_{31} & \hat{S}_{33} \end{bmatrix} e^{-ik_0 l} = \begin{bmatrix} t_f & r_b \\ r_f & t_b \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C3})$$

where the term $e^{-ik_0 l}$ is to eliminate the reference phase by setting the origin at the center of the metamaterial layer, and $t_f = t_b$ due to the reciprocity. For normal background medium $\tilde{\tau}_0 = \tilde{\kappa}_0 = 0$, we have

$$r_f - r_b = (\tilde{\kappa} - \tilde{\tau})k_0 l e^{-ik_0 l} \approx -\tilde{\tau} k_0 l e^{-ik_0 l} \quad (\text{C4})$$

in the long-wavelength limit. It is obvious that $r_f = r_b$ if the metamaterial is symmetric with $\tilde{\tau} = 0$.

FIG. 5. Theoretical values of reflection amplitude $|r|$ and phase $Arg(r)$ from both sides for the lossless case.

After obtaining the effective material parameters based on Appendix B, we theoretically calculate the reflection of the system. As shown in Fig. 5, exactly same amplitude but different phases are observed for the lossless case. Two dips of $|r|$ are located at 7.6 kHz and 11.0 kHz respectively, which excellently agrees with the simulated results shown in Fig. 1(b). For the lossy case of the modulus, the material parameters should be changed accordingly to be complex values. As shown in Fig. 1e, with 5% loss of the modulus, both the reflection amplitude and phase are different now, especially around the two dips. $|r_b|$ is also observed much smaller than $|r_f|$ at about 7.6 kHz. The agreement between

theoretical values and the simulated results (shown in Fig. 1(c)) shows the rationality of the present theory and the effective parameters retrieval method.

APPENDIX D: CALCULATION OF SCATTERING COEFFICIENTS

Once the frequency-domain wave field is tested, we first suppose that the wave pattern can be described as $w_1 = \alpha \cdot e^{ikx} + \beta \cdot e^{-ikx}$ and $w_2 = \gamma \cdot e^{ikx} + \delta \cdot e^{-ikx}$ on the incident side and transmitted side, respectively. Here, the wave is supposed to propagate along the x direction, and the origin is set at the center of the metamaterial layer. Then the complex coefficients α, β, γ and δ can be calculated by data fitting of the wave pattern at each frequency, for both the forward and backward case. Thus the scattering matrix is determined by

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} t_f & r_b \\ r_f & t_b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_f & \gamma_b \\ \beta_f & \beta_b \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_f & \alpha_b \\ \delta_f & \delta_b \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$$

where subscripts “ f ” and “ b ” correspond to forward and backward incident waves, respectively.

To numerically compute the scattering matrix S using COMSOL Multiphysics, perfect matched layers (PML) are used on both end of the beam, and plane waves are generated in the forward and backward directions respectively to generate the field pattern. Then similar processes as experiments are used to calculate the scattering matrix. It is noted that the complex coefficient D is zero due to the perfect absorption of waves by the PML. Therefore, we have $t_{f(b)} = \frac{\gamma_{f(b)}}{\alpha_{f(b)}}$ and $r_{f(b)} = \frac{\beta_{f(b)}}{\alpha_{f(b)}}$.

APPENDIX E: PHYSICAL MEANING OF THE SCATTERING COEFFICIENTS

Figure 6 illustrates the physical meaning of the scattering coefficients. In general, even / odd inputs will leads to even s_{ee} / odd s_{oo} scattering coefficients. However, due to the symmetric breaking effects in the present work, the cross-coupling scattering coefficient $s_c = s_{eo} = -s_{oe}$ between even input and odd output or vice versa. Thus we have,

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} t & r_b \\ r_f & t \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 2 + s_{ee} + s_{oo} & s_{ee} - s_{oo} + 2s_c \\ s_{ee} - s_{oo} - 2s_c & 2 + s_{ee} + s_{oo} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{E1})$$

Namely,

$$\begin{aligned} s_{ee} &= t - 1 + \frac{r_b + r_f}{2}, \\ s_{oo} &= t - 1 - \frac{r_b + r_f}{2}, \\ s_c &= \frac{r_b - r_f}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E2})$$

It is readily to see that for normal metamaterials with mirror symmetry, $s_c = \frac{r_b - r_f}{2} = 0$.

FIG. 6. Physical meaning of the scattering coefficients.

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